

Original article

Prevalence of Dyslipidemia among Apparently Healthy Students of Science Laboratory Technology in Bauchi State University Gadau

Hafizah S. Sulaiman,^{1*} Ibrahim A. A. Iliyasu,² Danjuma Yakubu,²

¹Department of Internal Medicine, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital Bauchi

²Department of Human Nutrition and Dietetics, Federal University of Health Sciences Azare

***Corresponding Author:** Hafizah S. Sulaiman: Email: sulaimanhafizahs@gmail.com Tel no. +234

Abstract

Background: Dyslipidemia is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD), with a rising global prevalence. Despite its health implications, limited studies have assessed dyslipidemia among apparently healthy university students in Nigeria. Objective: This study aimed to investigate the prevalence of dyslipidemia and its associated risk factors among students in the Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Bauchi State University Gadau. Materials & Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted involving 200 students (137 males, 63 females) aged 18–42 years. Anthropometric measurements (BMI) and fasting lipid profiles—total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) were analyzed. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 20.0, with independent t-tests comparing lipid profiles by gender. ANOVA with post-hoc tests assessed differences across BMI categories. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Results: Abnormal lipid profiles were observed in 18.2% (TC), 9.3% (TG), 19.8% (HDL-C), and 3.3% (LDL-C) of participants. No significant gender-based differences were found in mean TC, TG, HDL-C, or LDL-C levels. However, a significant difference was observed in the mean age of participants across BMI categories (underweight, normal weight, and overweight). Conclusion: The study highlights a notable prevalence of dyslipidemia among university students, emphasizing the need for regular lipid profile assessments and health promotion interventions to mitigate CVD risk.

Keywords: Body Mass Index, Cardiovascular Disease, Dyslipidemia, Prevalence, Risk Factors, Youths.

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Introduction

Dyslipidemia, defined by abnormal amounts of lipids in the blood including triglycerides, cholesterol, and phospholipids remain a serious worldwide health issue.¹ The disorder comprises a spectrum of lipid abnormalities, such as hypercholesterolemia, hypertriglyceridemia, and mixed dyslipidemia, which may come from both hereditary and environmental causes.² In industrialized nations, the major type of dyslipidemia is hyperlipidemia, typically related to high-calorie diets rich in saturated fats and trans fats, sedentary lifestyles, and other modifiable risk factors.³

Dyslipidemia is a key modifiable risk factor for atherosclerosis as well as ischemic heart disease

(IHD) which is a huge contributor to the raising levels of morbidity and death globally. Elevated levels of triglycerides (TG), total cholesterol (TC), and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C), along with low levels of high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), contribute to the pathogenesis of atherosclerosis, a process involving lipid deposition, endothelial dysfunction, and inflammation.⁴⁻⁵ The presence of dyslipidemia has been demonstrated to accelerate the formation of atherosclerotic plaques, increasing the risk of myocardial infarction, stroke, and other cardiovascular events.⁶ According to the World Health Organization (WHO), dyslipidemia is responsible for around 15% of ischemic heart disease and stroke cases, contributing to over four million deaths yearly.⁷

In 2012, CVD contributed 17.5 million fatalities, with dyslipidemia cited as one of the primary factors to this frightening number.⁸ Epidemiological studies suggest a constant, graded association between total plasma cholesterol concentrations and coronary risk, especially in younger persons.⁹ While lifestyle variables, such as food and physical exercise, account for 80% of lipid abnormalities, hereditary illnesses such as familial hypercholesterolemia contribute to the remaining 20%.¹⁰ Thus, the worldwide burden of cardiovascular disease (CVD) highlights the urgency of managing the predominantly modifiable dyslipidemia.

While dyslipidemia has generally been linked with industrialized nations, its incidence is growing in underdeveloped countries due to urbanization and the adoption of Western food and lifestyle practices. This epidemiological change has led to an increasing burden of CVD in areas that formerly had lower rates of dyslipidemia and associated disorders.¹¹⁻¹² Addressing the predominantly modifiable dyslipidemia involves extensive public health initiatives, including awareness campaigns, regular lipid monitoring, and lifestyle adjustments.

Despite the rising awareness of dyslipidemia and its detrimental effect, research on its prevalence and risk factors in particular subpopulations remain very few.¹³ This research investigated the lipid profiles and related variables among apparently healthy University students in the Department of Science Laboratory Technology at Bauchi State University, Gadau. The subpopulation of University students is chiefly characterized by major lifestyle changes, such as changing food

habits, reduced physical activity, and higher stress levels, which might predispose them to dyslipidemia.¹⁴⁻¹⁵ Understanding the lipid profiles and related variables among University students may be very vital for directing focused actions.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

This study was conducted at the Faculty of Science, Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Bauchi State University Gadau, located in Gadau town, Bauchi State, Northeast Nigeria.

Study Subjects

A random sampling technique was used to recruit 200 apparently healthy students from the Department of Science Laboratory Technology. Informed consent was obtained from each participant prior to the study.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The study included apparently healthy students from the Department of Science Laboratory Technology at Bauchi State University Gadau, aged 18–42 years, who provided informed consent. To ensure the sample consisted of individuals without underlying health conditions, participants were screened using a structured questionnaire. Those with known chronic illnesses (such as diabetes, hypertension, thyroid disorders, or cardiovascular diseases), those taking medications affecting lipid metabolism (like statins or hormonal contraceptives), pregnant students, and those with acute infections at the time of data collection were excluded from the study. This approach helped maintain a cohort of truly healthy participants for accurate assessment of dyslipidemia prevalence and associated risk factors.

Ethical Clearance

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Research and Ethical Clearance Committee of Bauchi State University Gadau, in accordance with the World Association Declaration of Helsinki's Ethical Principles for Medical Research Involving Human Subjects.

Anthropometric Measurements

Height, weight, and body mass index (BMI) were measured. Height was measured using a calibrated pole, while weight was measured using a

measuring scale. BMI was calculated as weight (kg) divided by height (m) squared according to techniques earlier described in published literature.¹⁶

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$. Descriptive statistics summarized the data, while independent t-tests (or Mann-Whitney U tests for non-normal data) compared lipid profiles between genders. Differences across BMI categories were assessed using ANOVA, followed by post-hoc tests where applicable. Pearson correlation evaluated relationships between variables, Normality was checked using Shapiro-Wilk, and variance homogeneity with Levene’s test.

Sample Collection

Blood samples were collected from consenting participants after an overnight fast of 10-12 hours. Five milliliters (5ml) of blood were collected from the cubital superficial vein by venipuncture.

Estimation of Total Cholesterol

Serum total cholesterol was determined using an enzymatic reaction as described by Meattini et al.¹⁷

Estimation of Serum Triglyceride

Serum triglyceride was determined using an enzymatic calorimetric method as described by Saleem et al.¹⁸

Estimation of High-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (HDL-C)

Serum HDL-C was determined using the Groove method as described by Ogura et al.¹⁹

Estimation of Low-Density Lipoprotein Cholesterol (LDL-C)

Serum LDL-C was calculated using the Friedewald formula as described by Hong et al.²⁰

Results:

This study investigated the lipid profile and prevalence of dyslipidemia among apparently healthy university students in the Department of Science Laboratory Technology. A total of 200 students participated in the study.

Demographic Characteristics:

Many participants were male (68.5%), with a mean age of 26.00 ± 5.09 years. The age distribution ranged from 18-42 years. The body mass index (BMI) classification revealed that 52% of participants were overweight, 44% had a normal weight, none was obese and 4% were underweight. (Table 1)

Lipid Profile results:

The mean values for total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), high-density lipoprotein cholesterol (HDL-C), and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-C) were 4.36 ± 1.01 mmol/L, 1.16 ± 0.44 mmol/L, 1.30 ± 0.28 mmol/L, and 2.53 ± 0.95 mmol/L, respectively. (Table 2)

Table 1: Demographic variables and Body Mass Index (BMI) of the participants

Variable	Number of participants (N)	Percentage (%)
<i>Sex</i>		
Male	137	68.5
Female	68	31.5
Total	200	100.0
<i>Age group (years)</i>		
18-22	58	29.0
23-27	76	38.0
28-32	43	21.5
33-37	16	8.0
38-42	7	3.5
Total	200	100.0
<i>BMI (Kg/m²)</i>		
Underweight ≤ 18.4	8	4.0
Normal weight 18.5-24.9	88	44.0
Overweight ≥ 25.0	104	52.0
Total	200	100.0

Table 2: Mean \pm Standard deviation of BMI and lipid profile parameters of the participants

Variable	Study participants	
	Mean \pm SD	
Body Mass Index (Kg/m ²)	26.00 ± 5.09	
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.36 ± 1.01	
Triglyceride (mmol/L)	1.16 ± 0.44	
HDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.30 ± 0.28	
LDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)	2.53 ± 0.95	

Lipid Profile Parameters based on Gender:

No significant differences were observed in the mean values of TC, TG, HDL-C, and LDL-C between males and females. However, the mean age was significantly higher in males than in females. (Table 3)

Lipid Profile Parameters Based on BMI:

The analysis of lipid profile parameters across BMI categories revealed a statistically significant difference was observed in the mean age of participants when compared across BMI categories.

($p < 0.01$). However, no significant variations were observed in the mean levels of total cholesterol (TC), triglycerides (TG), HDL-C, or LDL-C among these BMI categories (Table 4).

Table 3: Comparison of mean Age, BMI and Lipid Profile against the Gender of the participants.

Variable	Male (Mean \pm SD)	Female (Mean \pm SD)	p-value	Remark
Age (years)	26.45 \pm 5.53	25.00 \pm 3.80	0.01	S
Body Mass Index (Kg/m ²)	25.73 \pm 5.03	26.18 \pm 4.31	0.39	NS
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.40 \pm 1.01	4.29 \pm 1.01	0.35	NS
Triglyceride (mmol/L)	1.19 \pm 0.47	1.10 \pm 0.37	0.07	NS
HDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.31 \pm 0.29	1.27 \pm 0.26	0.23	NS
LDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)	2.54 \pm 0.98	2.51 \pm 0.90	0.81	NS

S=Statistically Significant while NS=Not Statistically Significant

Table 4: Comparison of Mean Age and Lipid profile parameters against BMI of the participants.

Variable	Underweight (Mean \pm SD)	Normal weight (Mean \pm SD)	Overweight (Mean \pm SD)	p-value	Remarks
Age (years)	24.44 \pm 4.29	25.19 \pm 4.34	26.79 \pm 5.60	0.001	S
Total cholesterol (mmol/L)	4.68 \pm 0.86	4.41 \pm 0.99	4.36 \pm 1.01	0.28	NS
Triglyceride (mmol/L)	1.04 \pm 0.51	1.14 \pm 0.48	1.19 \pm 0.40	0.35	NS
HDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)	1.34 \pm 0.29	1.29 \pm 0.29	1.30 \pm 0.27	0.77	NS
LDL-Cholesterol (mmol/L)	2.85 \pm 0.94	2.58 \pm 0.92	2.47 \pm 0.97	0.20	NS

S=Statistically Significant while NS=Not Statistically Significant

To further examine potential associations, we performed Pearson correlation analysis between BMI as a continuous variable and each lipid parameter. This additional analysis, which complements the group comparisons by assessing linear relationships, similarly showed no significant correlations between BMI and any of the measured lipid parameters (TC, TG, HDL-C, or LDL-C; $p < 0.01$) (Table 5). These findings from both analytical approaches - group comparisons and correlation analysis - consistently demonstrate no significant association between BMI and lipid profile measures in our study population. The dual analytical strategy was employed to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of potential BMI-lipid relationships through different but complementary statistical perspectives

Table 5: Pearson Correlation Coefficient of BMI and lipid profile parameters.

Variable	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value	Remark
BMI and TC	-0.035	0.484	NS
BMI and TG	0.088	0.078	NS
BMI and HDL	0.036	0.473	NS
BMI and LDL	-0.060	0.232	NS

S=Statistically Significant while NS=Not Statistically Significant

Correlation Analysis:

Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine potential associations between body mass index (BMI) and lipid profile parameters. The results revealed no statistically significant

correlations between BMI and any of the measured lipid parameters: total cholesterol ($r = -0.035$, $p = 0.484$), triglycerides ($r = 0.088$, $p = 0.078$), HDL-C ($r = 0.036$, $p = 0.473$), or LDL-C ($r = -0.060$, $p = 0.232$) (Table 5).

Table 6: Prevalence of Dyslipidemia among the participants

Variable	Number Observed (N)	Prevalence (%)
Dyslipidemia		
Yes	104	52.0
No	96	48.0
Total	200	100.0

The weak correlation coefficients (all $|r| < 0.1$) indicate minimal linear relationships between adiposity measures and lipid levels. This absence of significant associations persisted even when applying a more stringent significance threshold ($p < 0.01$) to account for multiple comparisons.

Prevalence of Dyslipidemia:

The study identified multiple lipid abnormalities among participants. Elevated total cholesterol (TC >5.2 mmol/L) was present in 18.2% of students, while 9.3% showed high triglyceride levels (TG >1.7 mmol/L). Low HDL-C (<1.1 mmol/L in males, <1.3 mmol/L in females) was observed in 19.8% of participants, and elevated LDL-C (>3.9 mmol/L) in 3.3%.

Table 7: The percentage prevalence of abnormal TC, TG, HDL & LDL among the participants.

Biochemical Parameters (mmol/L)	Percentage (%) (Abnormal)
Total Cholesterol (2.2-5.2)	18.2%
Triglyceride (≤ 1.7)	9.3%
HDL (1.1-1.5)	19.8%
LDL (≤ 3.9)	3.3%

Using the National Cholesterol Education Program (NCEP) Adult Treatment Panel III criteria, which defines dyslipidemia as having one or more abnormal lipid parameters, we found that 52% (104/200) of participants met this diagnostic threshold.

This comprehensive assessment accounts for the presence of any lipid abnormality rather than simply averaging individual prevalence rates,

providing a more accurate representation of dyslipidemia burden in this population.

The high prevalence of isolated lipid abnormalities, particularly low HDL-C (19.8%) and elevated TC (18.2%), suggests that university students may benefit from targeted screening and early lifestyle interventions to mitigate cardiovascular risk. The relatively low prevalence of elevated LDL-C (3.3%) indicates that this may be a less common abnormality in this young, apparently healthy population.

Discussion:

This study assessed the prevalence of dyslipidemia among apparently healthy students in the Department of Science Laboratory Technology at Bauchi State University Gadau. Dyslipidemia remains a critical modifiable risk factor for cardiovascular diseases (CVD), contributing to approximately 13% of global ischemic heart disease and stroke cases.²¹ Given that dietary and lifestyle factors influence nearly 80% of lipid abnormalities, understanding population-specific patterns is essential for early intervention and prevention strategies.²²

The observed prevalence rates in this study were 18.2% for elevated total cholesterol (TC), 9.3% for hypertriglyceridemia (TG), 19.8% for low HDL-C, and 3.3% for elevated LDL-C. These findings align with global trends but show notable variations when compared to other regions. For instance, a study among Chinese university students reported a lower overall dyslipidemia prevalence (13.17%), likely attributable to dietary patterns rich in vegetables and lean proteins.²³ In contrast, data from high-income countries such as the United States indicate higher prevalence rates, with the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) reporting that ~20% of adults aged 20–34 exhibit at least one form of dyslipidemia.²⁴ This discrepancy may reflect differences in dietary habits, physical activity levels, and socioeconomic factors.

Within Africa, the rising prevalence of dyslipidemia has been linked to urbanization and dietary shifts toward energy-dense processed foods.²⁵ However, some reported prevalence rates in prior studies require careful interpretation. For example, while one Ethiopian study cited a 67% dyslipidemia rate among university students, this figure appears exceptionally high and may reflect methodological differences or population-specific risk factors.²⁶ More plausible estimates from Ghana (41.1%)²⁷ and Nigeria (46.5–56.8%)²⁸ suggest moderate to high prevalence, consistent with our

findings. Regional variations likely stem from differences in dietary composition, physical activity, and genetic predispositions.

The mean BMI in our study ($26.00 \pm 5.09 \text{ kg/m}^2$) indicates a trend toward overweight and obesity, with 52.0% of participants falling into these categories a finding corroborated by prior Nigerian studies.²⁸⁻²⁹ Excess adiposity is a well-established driver of dyslipidemia, as it disrupts lipid metabolism and elevates cardiovascular risk.³⁰ However, our analysis revealed no significant differences in lipid parameters (TC, TG, HDL-C, or LDL-C) across BMI categories or between genders, consistent with findings from similar demographic groups.³¹⁻³² This suggests that in young adults, traditional risk factors like BMI and gender may have less pronounced effects on lipid profiles compared to older populations.

The high prevalence of dyslipidemia in this ostensibly healthy cohort underscores the need for proactive health interventions in academic settings. Routine lipid screening, coupled with targeted nutrition education and physical activity promotion, should be integrated into student health programs. Public health campaigns must also address the broader determinants of dyslipidemia, including the availability of healthy food options and opportunities for regular exercise.

Conclusion

This study highlights the prevalence of dyslipidemia among university students, reinforcing the importance of early screening and lifestyle modification in young adults. Future research should expand to larger, multi-center cohorts to validate these findings and explore region-specific determinants of dyslipidemia. While dietary factors (e.g., processed food consumption) are plausible contributors, further investigation is needed to establish causal relationships and inform context-specific interventions.

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